

To Cite:

Ade, N. P. (2025). Interrogating the Egalitarian Status of the Animate and Inanimate Forms of Nature in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Critical Analysis. *Archives of the Social Sciences: A Journal of Collaborative Memory, Research Letters*, Vol. 101, Issue 1, pp. 11053-11061. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15870103>

Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Philosophy, Faculty of Arts, University of Bamenda, Bamenda, Cameroon. Email: icare4unde@yahoo.com

Corresponding author

¹Department of Philosophy, Faculty of Arts, University of Bamenda, Bamenda, Cameroon. Email: icare4unde@yahoo.com

Peer-Review History

Received: 2nd May, 2025

Reviewed & Revised: 3rd May/2025 to 1st /July/2025

Accepted: 2nd July 2025

Published: 10th July 2025

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/archives-of-the-social-sciences-a-journal-of-collaborative-memory>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

License: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Interrogating the Egalitarian Status of the Animate and Inanimate Forms of Nature in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Critical Analysis

Nde Paul Ade¹

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15870103>

ABSTRACT

The radical and excessive interference of human practices in the non-human world within sub-Saharan Africa has significantly contributed to transforming favorable environmental conditions into adverse ones. This study reveals how the importance of the ecosystem and nature has consistently been underestimated, neglected, unrecognized, and morally overlooked. It emphasizes the practical complexity of dissociating humans from the space shared with other (non-human) entities within the same environment. Indigenous African contributions to environmental ethics are critically examined for their limited engagement with the human-nature relationship in sub-Saharan Africa—identified as a principal root cause of the ongoing environmental crisis in Africa and beyond. The study argues that only in cases involving essential and unavoidable needs for survival—such as food, water, and shelter—should humans extract resources from the richness and diversity of nature. The survival of communities across the region is shown to depend substantially on both living (animate) and non-living (inanimate) entities, which possess both physical and spiritual dimensions. The study concludes by recommending remedial strategies, including the adoption of technologies, ideological reforms, and sustainable practices such as biotechnology, bioremediation, ethical leadership, and the restoration of traditional African ecological values.

Keywords: African Environmental Ethics, Critical Evaluation, Egalitarian Status, Indigenous African Approaches, Nature, Sub-Saharan Africa.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most indigenous African conceptions of the “human” center on the understanding of a being that initially existed in isolation before establishing relationships with the environment. As Shutte (2009: 90–91) asserts, “the most important of these are the relationships we have with others.” Accordingly, the human-nature relationship emphasizes identifying and justifying the connections between humans and non-human elements of reality, such as seas, mountains, trees, and animals (Locke, 1954; Bourdillon, 1976; Menkiti, 1984; Bratton, 1993; Hughes, 1993; Murove, 2004; Kelbessa, 2005; Ramose, 2009; Imafidon, 2014). In this chapter, the terms “nature” and “environment” are used interchangeably. The term “Africa” refers specifically to indigenous sub-Saharan Africa. Although Africa is a continent characterized by vast cultural, ecological, economic, and political diversity, African perspectives are not confined to its geographic boundaries; elements of “Africanism” may also be identified beyond the continent, including in non-African contexts. The term “animate” denotes living beings, while “inanimate” refers to non-living entities.

SHERWAN
Publishers

The central problem addressed in this paper is the creation of a troubling, inhumane, unjust, and unacceptable void resulting from human interference with other components of nature, which has led to numerous harmful consequences for humans, non-humans, and the environment at large. The study seeks to address the following critical questions: To what extent have animate–inanimate relationships been adversely affected? What is the significance of animate and inanimate forms of nature? How are these forms interconnected and valued? What challenges, gaps, and shortcomings characterize their interactions? What remedial strategies can be adopted to bridge the divide between animate/human and inanimate/non-human aspects of nature? This study is structured into five sections. The first section explores the meanings of human/animate and non-human/inanimate forms of nature, drawing from both African and Western philosophical perspectives on the interconnectedness and inseparability of humans and nature within African environmental ethics. The second section provides conceptual clarifications on human and non-human aspects of nature. The third section focuses on recognizing the value of animate and inanimate forms of nature. The fourth section critically examines indigenous African approaches to human-nature relationships, highlighting gaps and inadequacies in existing ideologies, policies, and practices. The final section proposes strategies for ecological restoration and argues for the necessity of fostering a harmonious and interdependent relationship between human/animate and nature/inanimate entities within and beyond sub-Saharan Africa.

2. THE SIGNIFICATION OF ANIMATE/LIVING THINGS AND INANIMATE/NON-LIVING FORMS OF NATURE

Despite persistent appeals for a more harmonious relationship between animate and inanimate forms of existence—including calls for equal moral status for both—there remains a need to emphasize that humans possess a higher ontological degree of vitality, life, purpose, and potency than animals, plants, or inanimate objects (Tempels, 1959; Wiredu, 1994). Humans not only hold more legal rights than other species but also demonstrate the capacity to make vital decisions capable of transforming habitats and modes of living. Furthermore, human beings exercise planetary influence through unique abilities of cooperation and adaptability. While some social insects, such as bees and ants, exhibit cooperative behavior in large numbers, they do not possess the same level of cognitive flexibility as humans. This position diverges from Tempels' view of vital force as universally inherent, as he asserts: "it is because all beings is force and exist only in that it is force, that the category 'force' includes of necessity all beings: God, men living and departed, animals, plants, minerals" (Tempels, 1959: 52). Similarly, the African moral philosophy of Ubuntu—or Botho in Sesotho—extends beyond human relationships to include ethical engagement with the environment, especially non-human entities such as plants and animals, viewed from a non-anthropocentric perspective (LenkaBula, 2008: 37). Behrens (2014) also affirms that mountains, soil, rocks, rivers, and other natural features possess moral status, emphasizing that "African thought extends moral considerability to include all things that are part of the interconnected web of life—that is, all individual living things, groups of living things such as families, species, and ecosystems, as well as inanimate natural objects such as rivers and mountains" (2014b: 66). This perspective supports Taringa's conclusion that before engaging with elements of nature—such as hills, rivers, and rocks—ritual permission must be sought (Taringa, 2006: 201).

In many indigenous African moral systems, traditional rules and regulations prohibit indiscriminate deforestation and environmental exploitation. These norms are typically enforced during activities such as farming, fishing, and hunting. Scholars like Murove (2004) highlight ecological conservation as a foundational aspect of the Shona belief system, which includes observance of traditional rest days dedicated to halting all extractive activities. This practice allows the soil and ecosystems to regenerate naturally. Accordingly, the suspension of environmental exploitation for certain periods is seen as a practical expression of African environmental ethics (Murove, 2004: 195–215). Violators of these norms often face serious consequences, including banishment, land confiscation, or even capital punishment. Nevertheless, Etieyibo (2011: 32) argues that anthropocentric worldviews position humans at the pinnacle of all species and place them at the center of the universe. This perception further justifies the human tendency to interfere with, coordinate, and control both human and non-human entities, including the natural environment, through activities such as agriculture, logging, fishing, hunting, and resource extraction. In alignment with this, moral and relational philosophers—such as Ramose (1999: 49; 2009: 308), Tangwa (2004: 387–395), Bujo (2009b: 113–128), Ojomo (2011: 101–113), and Ugwuanyi (2011a: 1–10)—maintain that African environmental philosophy is rooted in relational systems. One such concept is Ukama, a doctrine highlighting interconnectedness, relativity, and the inseparability between humans and nature, as articulated by Murove (2004, 2009b). This relational dimension is evidenced by the attribution of moral status to all entities—human and non-human alike—in numerous African cultural traditions, as captured by Tangwa (2004) through the lens of "eco-bio-communitarian" ethics.

It is important to note that a fully realized human being, in many indigenous African contexts, is one whose existence is deeply rooted in connection with both humanity and the natural environment. In comparing Western and African environmental perspectives, Tangwa observes that "the Western worldview can be described as predominantly anthropocentric and individualistic," in contrast to its African counterpart, which is described as "eco-bio-communitarian" (Tangwa, 2004: 392). However, although Tangwa's representation of African environmental ethics incorporates the biosphere, humanity, and the supernatural, his characterization of Western environmental ethics as exclusively anthropocentric appears overly reductive, as non-anthropocentric elements also exist within Western environmental thought. Horsthemke (2005) argues that African environmental ethics can, at times, be anthropocentric, even within an eco-bio-communitarian framework, given that humans are often positioned as central actors whose activities primarily serve human interests (Horsthemke, 2005: 98). What becomes most

essential, therefore, is a critical examination of the moral foundations that inform human responsibility toward the environment (Ojomo, 2011: 103). Without a clear understanding of the ethical implications inherent in human-nature relationships, continued and indiscriminate interference with the environment may result in serious ecological and existential consequences for both humanity and nature. Given that moral perspectives on environmental issues frequently appear controversial, ambiguous, and context-dependent, it becomes necessary to critically assess whether non-human entities—such as water, soil, air, mountains, and rivers—should be granted moral consideration. The indigenous African worldview presents an inseparable bond between humans and nature. While Tangwa emphasizes the pre-colonial metaphysical framework, his writings consistently affirm the interdependence between humans and the environment, as reflected in his assertion: “the pre-colonial traditional metaphysical outlook can be described as eco-bio-communitarian, implying recognition and acceptance of interdependence between earth, plants, animals, and humans” (Tangwa, 2004: 389).

To ensure meaningful harmony between humans and nature—whether animate or inanimate—the well-being of both must be treated as a matter of broad and profound concern. Beyond meeting human survival needs and interests, the non-human and inanimate components of the environment deserve ethical attention and should be treated as ends in themselves. Nature, in this context, is not only instrumental but also a fulfillment of creation and an essential aspect of life’s broader purpose. Tempels’ conception of being, as presented in the “Bantu philosophy of existence,” further illuminates this view. Unlike the Western notion of being as static, the African or Bantu understanding portrays being as inherently dynamic. According to Tempels: “there is no idea among Bantu of being divorced from the idea of force; without force, being cannot be conceived” (Tempels, 1959: 51–52). This notion of vital force is directly linked to human-nature relations, suggesting that a spiritual energy resides in all forms of life, sustaining their existence. Because this force exists in both humans and animals, it reinforces a fundamental similarity and connection between them, establishing animals as integral to the broader natural order.

Recognizing this essential role of nature, Behrens argues: “an obvious implication of any position that holds that everything in nature is interdependent is that the well-being and continued survival of human beings is dependent on the health of the environment” (Behrens, 2011: 54). While such interconnectedness may appear anthropocentric—given the prioritization of human interests—it nonetheless supports efforts to strengthen ethical relationships that address the aspirations and well-being of both humanity and the natural world. In the same light, Shutte (2009), like Tempels (1959:89), points out the relations between humans and nature in traditional African ontology when Shutte states that, beings are closely linked with other vital beings and forces as he affirms:

In the traditional African view, the universe is not composed of things that interact with each other. It is seen, rather, as a world of forces interacting with other forces, a universal field of force. Everything that exists, stones, plants, animals, and persons too, is the focus and expression of interacting forces... They are also present in our emotions, ideas, muscles, and in our blood.

Consequently, this description, signals the existence of potency, energy, and soul in both the animate and inanimate facets of reality. In addition to this, the causes, manner, and source of forces are opined by Imafidon (2014) when he buttresses that, “the beings existing in the two realms of existence are lively and active in varying levels because they are vitalized, animated, or energized by an ontological principle or essence or force given by a supreme being” (38).

3. VALUING ANIMATE-INANIMATE FORMS OF NATURE IN AFRICAN ONTOLOGY

In African ontology, all forms of life—both animate and inanimate—are regarded as sacred. Simply stated, every human being and element of creation deserves respect in order to fulfill the purpose of existence, which is centered on living a good and meaningful life. Magesa (1997) emphasizes the importance of adopting a value system grounded in “the sacrality of life, respect for the spiritual and mystical nature of creation, and, especially, of the human person, the sense of the family, community, solidarity and participation; and an emphasis on fecundity and sharing in life, friendship, healing and hospitality” (Magesa, 1997: 52–53). The need to respect both human and non-human forms of life is evident, given the essential resources provided by nature—including shelter, food, and medicine—which serve both nature itself and the survival and continuity of humanity. Within this framework, the concept of harmonious living involves cultivating relationships between humans and non-humans to ensure survival and achieve meaningful, purposeful lives. This interpretation aligns with the theocentric approach to environmental ethics, which has been described as “the science of conduct determined by a divine conduct towards the environment” (Asiedu-Amoako, 2013: 416). According to indigenous sub-Saharan African perspectives, God and nature are spiritually interconnected and ethically inseparable. Human actions toward the environment are believed to mirror moral obligations toward God. This theological stance is based on the understanding that God, as the supreme being whose existence is assumed without question, should be revered through the treatment of nature (Ekanola, 2006: 77). Logically, since God is regarded as the creator of all life and the ultimate judge of human activity, it is concluded that divine presence spiritually permeates the natural world.

This belief also affirms that God’s teleological intention was for humans, land, water, plants, and animals to coexist in a balanced, respectful relationship—one that acknowledges the intrinsic spiritual value of all forms of life. Examples such as the

spiritual efficacy of the python, the tortoise, and various medicinal plants used in the treatment of mental illness, blindness, and metaphysical afflictions reflect the sacred status attributed to nature within African environmental ethics (Taringa, 2006: 197). Accordingly, respect for all aspects of creation is a foundational ethical principle that binds divinity, humanity, and the natural world (Oladipo, 2004: 356; Bourdillon, 1976: 277). Further support for this perspective is found in the work of Oruka (1997b), who argues for the moral and ecological importance of every component of the environment. He maintains that “it is not scientifically plausible to dismiss any member of the ecological domain as non-useful. The sensible position to take is that the whole ecosystem balances itself, and that balance should be ascertained and hence the concern to maintain and promote biodiversity” (Oruka, 1997b: 250). Similarly, Udeani (2008: 67) argues for a three-sided spiritual relation involving God, humans, and the environment as the basis of African worldview when he opines that:

Traditional African spirituality and ethics are, in a way, a triangular relationship which incorporates, firstly, the natural beings in their relationship with other natural beings. Secondly, it pertains to the relationship between natural and spiritual beings, and then that of existing spiritual beings in their relation to one another. Ethical and moral issues go beyond the issues that arise within the context of interactions among natural beings. That is to say, issues of ethics do not only come into question when considering the implications of human actions vis-à-vis other humans and animals. It has wider and deeper dimensions.

A common belief among the Igbo of Nigeria holds that, the earth embodies almost everything as it gives life, herbs, and food. Several animals like the python, owl, vulture, parrot, ram, monkey, tiger, crocodile, and tortoise, are considered sacred, manifesting spiritism and closely linked to the clan (Kanu, 2013, 2015a, 2021; Aniako, 1979, 2002). Similarly, other ethnic groups of Cameroon like the Mankon, Balikumbat and Bafut people consider the animals cited above as possessing sacredness (According to the Igbo and Balikumbat people, the python is considered as a messenger from the gods and ancestors that ought not to be killed). There are taboos which prevent these animals from harm or being killed by humans. This cultural belief is valuable for preserving and enhancing biodiversity. For instance, python eggs are used for the fabrication of other medicines, while forests serve as habitats for animals, spirits, deities, areas for sacrifices and worship. Therefore, the act of sparing the lives of such animals shows the inseparable connection between humans and nature which goes a long way to ensure continuity of varied forms of existence which play valuable roles for humans and nature.

4. CRITIQUING INDIGENOUS AFRICAN APPROACHES TO ANIMATE-INANIMATE RELATIONS

To a significant extent, various forms of human interference in the environment—alongside inefficient, incomplete, and unproductive mitigation strategies, particularly within the African context—have adversely affected human-nature relationships. Nature, therefore, should be regarded as a manifestation of divine design, one that ought not to be exploited or manipulated for any purpose, given the intrinsic interconnectedness and interdependence among the various components of creation (Pope Francis, 2015; Global Buddhist Climate Change Collective). Sustainable development remains achievable through minimizing the ecological footprint of construction activities, conserving and restoring degraded environments, and promoting attitudes and policies that support harmony between humans and nature. Such measures include the prohibition of indiscriminate tree felling, the excessive use of chemical fertilizers, and the overexploitation of natural resources through fishing and hunting. As emphasized by Pope Francis (2015), the ecological crisis represents not only an environmental issue but also a deeply rooted spiritual and moral problem, necessitating corresponding ethical responses. This perspective is reinforced in his observation: “in this shallow, short-sighted culture that we have created, bereft of a shared vision, it is foreseeable that, once certain resources have been depleted, the scene will be set for new wars albeit under the guise of noble claims” (Pope Francis, 2015: 17).

Revisiting various African indigenous belief systems remains a valuable endeavor, particularly when emphasizing cultural values rooted in respect for traditions, rather than dismissing them as fetishistic or superstitious. The global community should be encouraged to promote indigenous knowledge systems centered on environmental conservation as a means of safeguarding both humanity and the ecosystem. For instance, educational curricula beginning at the primary level should integrate nature studies with a strong focus on environmental conservation, preservation, and restoration. Traditional leaders—regarded as key stakeholders and custodians of indigenous culture—ought to play a catalytic role in environmental protection by enforcing strict measures to limit the overexploitation of natural resources. One example includes the designation of traditional holidays during which activities such as farming, fishing, logging, and hunting are prohibited, with penalties imposed on violators to ensure effective ecological regeneration. In addition, national governments are encouraged to support, institutionalize, and employ specialists in indigenous knowledge systems. Educational institutions at the secondary, vocational, and university levels should incorporate the study of indigenous ecological values into their curricula, recognizing that timely and sustainable resource management is critical to addressing challenges in human-environment interactions (Thomas, 2003:

989–998). African communal values such as Ujamaa (Brotherhood), Ukama (“I am because of the entire cosmic web”), and Ubuntu (“I am because we are”) should also be mainstreamed, as they affirm the interconnection and mutual influence between all forms of life, both human and non-human. According to Ukeh (2016), human actions toward other people also impact animals, plants, stones, and other elements of the natural world. Citing Benedict XVI, Ukeh affirms that “every violation of solidarity and civic friendship harms the environment” (Ukeh, 2016: 81). This perspective is further supported by Agbakwuo (2013), who asserts that “communalism is central to African ontology, concept of person and socio-anthropology. Any behavior that negates it is ethically wrong. Integral to the African understanding of communalism are human participation and solidarity... Africans do not see themselves as individuals living independently, but rather as people living in a community interdependently, with communal responsibilities. The web of interdependence and interrelatedness is intrinsic in the African hierarchy of beings” (Agbakwuo, 2013: 161).

According to eco-centric thinkers (Gupta, 1980; Oruka, 1997b; Bujo, 1998; Nnamani, 2005; Tangwa, 1996, 2004; Chivaura, 2006a, 2006b; Dafni, 2006; Appiah, 2007; Naess, 2008; Uche, 2009; Masolo, 2010; Ojomo, 2010; Atieyibo, 2011; Chuka, 2012; Ekwealor, 2012; Matsika, 2012; Asiedu, 2013; Gyekye, 2013; Obianika, 2015; Okonkwo et al., 2016; Ikechukwu, 2021), ecological thought fundamentally rejects the notion that human beings are distinct and superior to other elements of the environment. Instead, it promotes a more unified perspective that situates humans as integral parts of the natural world. From the standpoint of ecological egalitarianism, the interconnectedness between humans and the broader biosphere is both indispensable and non-negotiable. All life forms—humans, animals, plants, and others—are understood to possess intrinsic value and equal rights to exist, develop, and coexist peacefully. This assertion supports the argument that the non-human world should not be exploited merely for anthropocentric goals. The richness and diversity of nature contribute significantly to the realization of ethical values and to the articulation of their deeper meanings. Egalitarian environmental philosophers advocate that only when vital and unavoidable survival needs arise should humans draw upon the natural world’s resources. However, due to widespread and excessive human interference, numerous previously stable ecological conditions have deteriorated. The negative consequences include runoff, soil degradation, air and water pollution, broader environmental contamination, and the extinction of rare species. To address these issues effectively, a fundamental shift in mentality and ideology is required—one that places ethical value on all life forms rather than prioritizing material prosperity or higher standards of living. Activities such as indiscriminate soil tilling, unregulated hunting and fishing, and the killing of animals—particularly endangered species—must be strictly controlled or prohibited. Additionally, contemporary policies related to ideology, economy, and technology must be reevaluated and restructured to move away from frameworks that have historically contributed to ecological degradation. As emphasized by Devall and Sessions (1985), a transformative paradigm is necessary to reestablish harmony between humans and the natural environment.

Ecology contributes to the generation of wealth and provides a practical framework for sustainable human lifestyles. In this context, Naess (2008) emphasizes that the value of ecology lies in its foundation as a philosophical discipline—one that embodies a well-articulated form of wisdom synthesizing both theoretical insight and pragmatic application. This philosophical approach underscores the necessity of active engagement from multiple sectors in recognizing the richness of biodiversity and in fostering a healthier and more balanced ecosystem. The participation of all living entities is essential—not only for the broader ecological good but also for their intrinsic worth. Both human and non-human life forms, including microorganisms such as soil bacteria, play indispensable roles in maintaining the proper functioning of ecosystems due to their unique ecological functions and inherent value. Given the diverse values that reinforce the interconnectedness between humanity and nature, it becomes imperative to avoid underestimating the wealth and diversity found in the natural world. Exploitation should be limited strictly to situations involving essential needs for survival, such as food, water, and shelter—resources that are fundamental for growth and are prerequisites for human continuity. It is important to acknowledge that the definition of vital needs may vary depending on geographic location and the level of technological development. In contemporary society, many functions rely on advanced technologies that were not necessary in the past. In contrast, non-essential needs—such as acquiring luxury items like new automobiles or constructing private swimming pools—represent desires that are not necessary for survival and can be foregone without compromising well-being. Prioritizing the fulfillment of only essential needs significantly reduces the extent and intensity of human interference with the natural environment, thereby promoting more sustainable human-nature relationships. From this perspective, it is important to concur with Mechant (1992: 87) by affirming that, humans are supposed to be part of nature and to live peacefully with it and not by always attempting to dominate or subdue it. Insistently, she adds:

Re-inhabiting the land as ‘dwellers in it’ rejects industrial society as the world paradigm for development and entails leaving vast tracts of land as wilderness, people can live their lives as ‘future primitives’ by withdrawing from developed land and allowing it to reestablish itself as wilderness....For each ecological religion, the guideline for use should be human carrying capacity.

5. WAY FORWARD

Irrespective of the fact that statistics indicate an increase in more human interferences into nature and carrying capacity today, resulting from evidences of more occupancy on earth, visible through food shortages, soil degeneration, lack of quality water, among others, humans are hereby called up as dwellers of nature to manifest a higher sense of responsibility by ensuring that, the numerical value of humans does not in any way affects the local environment in which every society inhabits negatively. It is worth noting that, the reduction of peoples ecological consciousness contributes immensely to a drastic drop in our consumptive habits, reduces forms of environmental injustices, water pollution, unfair treatment of minorities and the underprivileged. Therefore, all sorts of negative lifestyles impacting nature should be revisited. Basing on Devall's (1988: 83) *Simple in Ideas, Rich in Ends: Practicing Deep Ecology*, in which he advocates for the implementation of new and healthier lifestyles of humans vis-à-vis nature, is prompted by the fact that, a majority of humans manifest deviant attitudes from an average behavior expected to be exemplary in the dominant culture.

Another solution for a change in mentality about ecological concerns would be the ability to resist advertisements and appeals geared toward more consumption under the pretext of maintaining the economy, or the introduction of "the absence of novophilia", which Naess (2008: 83, 92) defines as, "the love of what is new simply because it is new". So, a more compassionate lifestyle, simplicity, which is not attributed to self-denial (alienation) and respect for non-human creatures are recommendable in bridging the gap between humans and non-humans. Similarly, from a greater extent, nature conservationists like biologists, consider the adoption of deep ecology as a means to facilitate the selection and designation of barriers and better management strategies of nature reserves, parks, and wild lands. Even the impacts of technology on the environment can be easily determined through the introduction of ecological consciousness and ecological restoration. However, given the current state of affairs portraying various varied forms of environmental crises, derived from human activities and partly related to the cleaning up of pollution, the act of preserving and conserving rapidly growing habitats becomes urgent. In addition, the endeavor to prevent past mistakes of various natures, the appeal to biotechnology is a panacea in providing a new, effective, and more innovative system that minimizes the level of human interference and impacts on the environment, while addressing other human environmental concerns simultaneously. Similar to this biotechnological approach to ecological restoration, is an effective method termed "Bioremediation", considered by Lenhard, Skeen, & Brouns (1995: 159) as, "the use of microorganisms and other living species to destroy, immobilize, or otherwise transform contaminants to less hazardous forms". Since human activities on the immediate environment and in nature are in most cases considered hostile and unacceptable, irrespective of the reason, the principal preoccupation of environmentalists should focus mostly on ecological restoration. Hence, bioremediation, being one of the newest technologies and most effective method, plays a catalyst role in restoring destroyed natural environment by human activities.

However, following the afore-examined premises, there is an urgent need to revisit various traditional African approaches in order to reinstate traditional values focused on the preservation of nature, since modernism and urbanization have paralyzed African indigenous beliefs immensely. Moreover, taking cognizance of taboos and habitats signal the spiritual, environmental, and socio-cultural importance of animals and other inanimate objects in the preservation of the ecosystem (Gyamfi, 2011: 145-155). The beliefs in sacred days (traditional holidays) as evident in Igbo communities and the grass fields of Cameroon, boost the manner in which the environment is composed, used, and preserved. Similarly, the Shona beliefs equally uphold the environment as sacred and as means of multiplying agricultural output in present day societies by discouraging the destruction of the environment (Mhaka, 2015). In a similar vein, world religions like Buddhism, Confucianism, Taoism, Shinto, Jainism, Hinduism, Judaism, Islamism, Indigenous traditions and Christianity, have signaled the need for a universal consciousness of humans vis-à-vis the ecosystem by proposing numerous remedial outcomes. Ubuntu, understood as "warmth, empathy, understanding, communication, interaction, participation, reciprocation and harmony (Mkize, 2003), should be intensified since it ties with the values of human-nature links as well as kicks against discrimination of any sort (Museka & Madondo, 2012). Finally, it is worth stating that, "finding ways to develop a sustainable relationship with nature requires not only the engagement and determination of scientists and political leaders, but also moral leadership that religious institutions are in a position to offer" (Dasgupta & Ramanathan, 2014: 1457).

6. CONCLUSIONS

Finally, one particular remedy is insufficient to resolve all environmental crises on earth, since every situation is weighed based on its own merits and particularity. The environment and nature deserve to be well taken care of, irrespective of the persons or organs in charge (Macnaphen & Urry, 1995; Magesa, 1997; Ugwuani, 2011a; Mangena, 2013). Humans are obligated to save nature from extinction both for humanity's sake and for nature's. The growth of agriculture in sub-Saharan Africa, understood as the tending of plants and animals through their life cycle has been a catalyst in systematically transforming nature and modifying its course for human interests. If humans fail in this significant task of cohabiting pacifically with nature, then, they should be held accountable for destroying what was meant to be preserved, protected, and saved especially for future generations. The destruction of nature by humans is somehow connected to "killing Humanity and God". So, the adoption of ideologies, technologies and practices such as bioremediation, moral leadership, biotechnology, reinstating ancient African traditional values related to ecological restoration like Shona beliefs and Ubuntu (understood as "warmth, empathy, understanding, communication, interaction, participation, reciprocation and harmony) will be salutary remedies for the present and future generations. This connection is vital based on the fact that, humans depend on nature for food, medicine, shelter and

survival. Consequently, destroying nature amounts to destroying humanity and God, following the pantheistic conception that God resides in nature and is an integral part of it (Nature), as Nietzsche (2006) once stated:

God is dead. God remains dead and we have killed him. How shall we comfort ourselves, the murderers of all murderers? What was holiest and mightiest of the world that has yet owed his blood to death under our knives: who will wipe the blood off us? What water is there for us to clean ourselves? What festivals of atonement, what sacred games shall we have to invent? Is not the greatness of this deed too great for us? Must we ourselves not become gods simply to appear worthy of it? (125).

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Adu-Gyamfi, Y. (2011). Indigenous Beliefs and Practices in Ecosystem Conservation: Response of the Church, *Scriptum*, 107, 145-155.
2. Agbakwuo, J.O. (2013). *The African: His Religion and Cosmology*, Umuahia, Lumen Press.
3. Aniako, C. (1979). "Ancestral Legitimation in Igbo Art", *West African Religion*, Volume 18, Number 2, 13-15.
4. Aniako, C. (2002). Art in the Culture of Igboland: A Survey of the Igbo Nation, Onitsha, Africana First Publishers, 300-307.
5. Appiah-Opoku, S. (2007). "Indigenous Beliefs and Environmental Stewardship: A Rural Ghana Experience", *Indigenous Knowledge and Development Monitor*, Volume 7, Number 3, 15-17.
6. Asiedu-Amoako, S. (2013). "Christianity and Ecology: Towards a Theocentric Ecological Ethics for Ghana", *Prime Journal of Social Science*, Volume 2, Number 8, 415-421.
7. Behrens, K. (2010). "Exploring African Holism with Respect to the Environment", *Environmental Values*, Volume 19, Number 4, 465-484.
8. Behrens, K. (2011). *African Philosophy, Thought and Practice and their Contribution to Environmental Ethics*, Unpublished Doctoral Thesis, University of Johannesburg, <https://hdl.handle.net/10210/5330> (accessed 19 January 2022).
9. Bookchin, M. (1990a). *Remaking Society: Pathways to a Green Future*, Boston, South End Press.
10. Bookchin, M. (1990b). *The Philosophy of Social Ecology: Essays in Dialectical Naturalism*, Montreal, Black Rose Books.
11. Bookchin, M. (2003). "Death of a Small Planet: It's Growth That's Killing Us", *Institute for Social Ecology*, <http://www.socielecology.org/article.php?story=20031117103522543>. (accessed May 10, 2024).
12. Bookchin, M. (2008). "Social Ecology versus Deep Ecology", *Environmental Ethics: Readings in Theory and Application*, United States, 243.
13. Bourdillon, M. (1976). *The Shona Peoples*, Gweru, Mambo Press.
14. Bratton, S.P. (1993). "Christian Ecotheology and the Old Testament", *Environmental Ethics: Divergence and Convergence*, New York, McGraw-Hill.
15. Bujo, B. (1998). *The Ethical Dimensions of Community: The African Model and the Dialogue between North and South*, Nairobi, Pauline's Publishing Company.
16. Bujo, B. (2009b). "Is there a Specific African Ethic? Toward a Discussion with Western Thought", *African Ethics: An Anthology of Comparative and Applied Ethics*, Pietermaritzburg, University of KwaZulu-Natal Press, 113-128.
17. Chivaura, V.G. (2006a). *African Indigenous Worldviews and Ancient Wisdom: A Conceptual Framework for Development in Southern Africa*, *Indigenous Peoples Wisdom and Power: Affirming our Knowledge through Narratives*, Burlington, VT, Ashgate Publishing Company, 213-224.
18. Chivaura, V.G. (2006b). "Hundu/Ubuntu: A Sustainable Approach to Endogenous Development, Bio-Cultural Diversity and Protection of the Environment in Africa", Presented at Papers International Conference, Geneva, 229-240.
19. Chuka, O.A. (2012). "From Traditionalism to Modernism: A Study of the Problem of Environment in Africa", *Scientific Research*, Volume 2, Number 4, 272-273.
20. Dafni, A. (2006). "On the Typology and Worship Status of Sacred Trees with a Special Reference to the Middle East", *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, Volume 2, Number 26, 1-14.
21. Dasgupta, P., Ramanathan, V. (2014). "Pursuit of the Common Good", *Science*, Volume 345, Number 6203, 1457-1458.
22. Devall, B., Sessions, G. (1985). *Deep Ecology*, Salt Lake City, Peregrine Books, 231-234.
23. Devall, B. (1998). *Simple in Means, Rich in Ends: Practicing Deep Ecology*, Salt Lake City, Peregrine Smith Books, 83.
24. Ekanola, A.B. (2006). *Metaphysical Issues in African Philosophy: Core Issues in African Philosophy*, Ibadan, Hope Publications, 74-89.
25. Ekwealor, C.J. (2012). "Ndu mmili ndu azu (Live and Let Live)", *African Environmental Ethics and Values*, Volume 3, Number 1, 90-106.
26. Etieyibo, E. (2011). "An Outline of an Ecumenical Environmental Ethics" *The Trumpeter*, Volume 27, Number 3, 48-59.
27. Francis, P. (2015). *Laudatio Si (Praise be to You)*, Papal Encyclical on Climate, 17, <https://www.ewtn.com>. (accessed May 10, 2024).
28. Francis, P. (2020). *Fratelli Tutti*, Social Encyclical on Fraternity and Social Friendship, Vatican City, Libreria Editrice Vaticana.
29. Gupta, S.S. (1980). *Sacred Trees across Cultures and Nations*, Calcutta, Indian Publications.
30. Horsthemke, K. (2015). *Animals and African Ethics*, New York, Palgrave, Macmillan.
31. Hughes, J.D. (1993). "The Ancient Roots of our Ecological Crisis", *Environmental Ethics: Divergence and Convergence*, New York, McGraw-Hill.
32. Ifesieh, M. (1989). *Religion at the Grassroots*, Studies in Igbo Religion, Enugu, Fourth Dimension Publishing Company Limited.
33. Ikechukwu, A.K. (2021). *African Indigenous Ecological Knowledge Systems, Religion, Philosophy, and the Environment*, Association of the Promotion of African Studies (APAS), Trebleclef Lane, Silver Spring, Maryland, United States of America.
34. Imafidon, E. (2014). *On the Ontological Foundations of Social Ethics in African Traditions*, *Ontological Ethics: New Essays in African Meta-Ethics*, Lanham, Lexington Books, 37-54.
35. Kanu, A. (2013). "Dimensions of African Cosmology", *Journal of African Philosophy, Culture and Religion*, Volume 2, Number 2, 533-555.
36. Kanu, A. (2015a). *African Philosophy: An Ontologico-Existential Hermeneutic Approach to Classical and Contemporary Issues*, Nigeria, Augustinian Publications.
37. Kanu, A. (2021). *Igwebuike: An Operative Condition of African Philosophy, Religion and Culture: Towards a Thermodynamic Transformative Ontology*, Maiden Inaugural Lecture Delivered on 21st February 2021 at Tansian University, Umunya, Autograde, Abuja.
38. Katz, E. (1992). "The Big Lie: Human Restoration of Nature", *Research in Philosophy and Technology*, 12, 231-242.
39. Kelbessa, W. (2005). "The Rehabilitation of Indigenous Environmental Ethics in Africa", *Diogenes*, Volume 207, 17-34.
40. Lenhard, R.J., Skeen, R.S., Brouns, T.M. (1995). "Contaminants

- at U.S DOE Sites and their Susceptibility to Bioremediation”, *Bioremediation: Science and Application*, SSSA Special Publication, 43, Madison, 159.
42. LenkaBula, P. (2008). “Beyond Anthropocentricity-Botho/Ubuntu and the Quest for Ecological Justice in Africa”, *Religion and Theology*, Volume 15, Number 3-4, 375-394.
 43. Light, A. (2000). “Ecological Restoration and the Culture of Nature: A Pragmatic Perspective”, *Restoring Nature: Perspectives from the Social Sciences and Humanities*, Washington, Island Press, 56-57.
 44. Locke, J. (1954). *Essays on the Law of Nature*, Oxford, Clarendon Press.
 45. Macnaghten, P., Urry, J. (1995). “Towards a Sociology of Nature”, *Sociology*, 29, 2, 203-221.
 46. Magesa, L. (1997). *African Religion: The Moral Traditions of Abundant Life*, New York, Orbis Books.
 47. Mangena, F. (2013). “Discerning Moral Status in the African Moral Environment”, *Phronimon*, Volume 14, Number 2, 25-44.
 48. Masolo, D.A. (2010). *Self and Community in a Changing World*, Bloomington, Indiana University Press.
 49. Matsika, C. (2012). *Traditional African Education: It’s Significance to Current Educational Practices with Special Reference to Zimbabwe*, Gweru, Mambo Press.
 50. Mawere, M. (2012). “Buried and forgotten but not Dead: Reflections on Ubuntu in Environmental Conservation in South Eastern Zimbabwe”, *Afro Asian Journal of Social Sciences*, Volume 3, Number 2, 1-20.
 51. Mechant, C. (1992). *Radical Ecology: The Search for a Livable World*, New York, Routledge, 87.
 52. Menkiti, I.A. (1984). *Person and Community in African Traditional Thought*, *African Philosophy: An Introduction*, New York, University Press of America, 171-181.
 53. Mhaka. (2015). “Attachment Theory and KurovaGuva”, *Zambezia*, Volume 36, Number i/ii, 258-265.
 54. Mkize, D.L. (2003). “Towards an Afrocentric Approach to Psychiatry”, *South African Journal of Psychiatry*, 9, 3-6.
 55. Murove, M.F. (2004). “An African Commitment to Ecological Conservation: The Shona Concept of Ukama and Ubuntu”, *The Mankind Quarterly*, Volume 45, Number 2, 195-215.
 56. Museka, G. & Madondo, M.M. (2012). “The Quest for a Relevant Environmental Pedagogy in the African Context: Insights from Unhul Ubuntu Philosophy”, *Journal of Ecology and the Natural Environment*, Volume 4, Number 10, 258-265.
 57. Naess, A. (2008). “Ecosophy: Deep versus Shallow Ecology”, *Environmental Ethics: Readings in Theory and Application*, Unites States, Thomson Wardsworth, 83-220.
 58. Nietzsche, F.W. (2006). “The Gay Science”, *The Nietzsche Reader*, Malden, Blackwell, 125.
 59. Nnabugwu, I. (2021). *The Sacredness of Trees in Igboland-Achara, Ihechiowa: Ahara, Mbauzie, Uga, Aguata*, www.nwanemnews.com (accessed February 10, 2025).
 60. Nnamani, A.G. (2005). *Ethics of the Environment: General, Special and Professional*, Ibadan, Heinemann Educational Books, 391-400.
 61. Obianika, C.E. et al. (2015). “Economic Trees in Igbo Culture: A Morphosemantic Analysis and Socio-Philosophical and Economic Interpretations”, *School Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, Volume 3, Number 3C.
 62. Ojomo, P.A. (2010). “An African Understanding of Environmental Ethics”, *Thought and Practice: A Journal of the Philosophical Association of Kenya*, Volume 2, Number 2, 49-63.
 63. Okonkwo, E. et al. (2016). *A Documentation of some Traditional Aspects of Wood Consumption in Amocha, Nigeria*, Sage Open, Sagepub.com.
 64. Oladipo, O. (2004). *Religion in African Culture: Some Conceptual Issues*, *A Companion to African Philosophy*, Malden, Blackwell, 356-357.
 65. Oruka, H.O. (1997b). *Practical Philosophy: In Search of an Ethical Minimum*, Nairobi, East African Educational Publishers.
 66. Parker, K. (1996). “Pragmatism and Environmental Thought”, *Environmental Pragmatism*, New York, Routledge, 28.
 67. Ramose, M.B. (2009). *Ecology through Ubuntu, African Ethics: An Anthology of Comparative and Applied Ethics*, Pietermaritzburg, University of KwaZulu Natal Press, 308-314.
 68. Scherer, D. (1995). “The Practice of Ecological Restoration”, *Environmental Ethics*, 17, 359-380.
 69. Shutte, A. (2009). *Ubuntu as the African Ethical Vision*, *African Ethics: An Anthology of Comparative and Applied Ethics*, Pietermaritzburg, University of KwaZulu Natal Press.
 70. Tangwa, G.B. (1996). *Democracy and Meritocracy: Philosophical Essays and Talks from an African Perspective*, Galda & Wilch Verlag.
 71. Tangwa, G.B. (2004). *Some African Reflections on Biomedical and Environmental Ethics*, *A Companion to African Philosophy*, Malden, Blackwell Publishing, 387-395.
 72. Taringa, N.T. (2006). “How Environmental is African Traditional Religion?” *Exchange*, Volume 35, Number 2, 190-215.
 73. Tempels, P. (1959). *Bantu Philosophy*, Paris, Présence Africaine, 52.
 74. Thomas, W.H. (2003). “One Last Chance: Tapping Indigenous Knowledge to Produce Sustainable Conservation Policies”, *Future*, 35, 989-998.
 75. Ugwuanyi, L.O. (2011a). “Advancing an Environmental Ethics through the African Worldview”, *Proceedings of the First International Technology, Education and Environment Conference*, African Society for Scientific Research, 1-10, <https://www.hrmars.com/admin/pics/327.pdf> (accessed 10 November 2023).
 76. Ukeh, C.O. (2016). *Spirit between Man and God: An Igbo African Christian Appreciation*, Enugu, Snaap Press, 81.
 77. Wiredu, K. (1994). *Philosophy, Humankind and the Environment*, *Humanity and Ecology*, Nairobi, ACTS Press, 30-48.

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s). Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.